

EVENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Background of the project

Overview of the business domain

Event management is the coordinated effort behind planning, organizing, and executing various events or features. This includes weddings, corporate meetings, fundraisers, sporting events, fashion shows, and much more.

Event Script is one of the newly commenced event management companies based in Jaffna. They have been known as elegant event planners with creative ideas. Their Vision is “Be a guest in your own event.” They are always ready to make the events much more beautiful and stunning. They currently are providing their services in Trincomalee, Colombo and Jaffna. This company which was inceptioned in June 2018 is a sole proprietorship owned by Ms. Sinthuja Vijayarajah

Currently, they are offering services for birthday parties, weddings, get together events and other family events. Their event services include Catering, Decoration, Photography, Music and bands, and Invitation card designing.

Overview of the current system

Currently, event script manages all their activities through manual paper-based system and Microsoft Office Application Environment.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

From this current process, they face some challenges.

- Difficult to inquire and gather information about their services.
- Time-consuming
- Data redundancy

- Difficult to manage payment.
- Difficult to check any expenses related to past events.
- Inconvenience in maintaining the employee details and salary calculations.
- Human errors

Requirement Analysis

Functional Requirements of the system is as follows:

- View services
- User Login & Logout
- Send an event booking request
- View, Edit, Delete the request
- Managing the employee details
- Center management

Proposed system & objectives

To overcome the limitations of the existing system main modules were identified for this Event Management System. They are Client management, Employee maintenance, Service management, Booking and Center Management.

Objectives of the system are as follows:

- Clients should be able to easily to inquire about the services provided by
- Event Script.
- Save time by doing online discussions with the clients and searching for
- available time slots online.
- Eliminate data redundancy with centralized data records.
- Easy to manage payment system.
- Ability to check any expenses related to past events.

- Easy to maintain employee details and salary calculations.
- Avoid human errors.
- Acquire more customers by using the proposed system.

System Design

Data design

Figure 1 below indicates the Entity-Relationship diagram, which displays the relationship among entities.

Figure 1: ER Diagram

Process Design

Figure 2: Use case Diagram for Admin

User interface design

Figure 3: Home page of Event script

System Development

System development Requirement

At the System Development phase, different software tools were used to develop the system. **Laravel framework** was used as it is a powerful MVC PHP framework (*MVC: Model, View, Controller App organization explained 2017, Laravel Tutorial: Step by Step Guide to Building Your First Laravel Application 2012*), designed for developers who need a simple and elegant toolkit to create fully-featured web applications.

Database & Interface Development

SQL server was selected as a database management system for this project. MySQL is free and open-source software under the terms of the GNU General Public License (Tutorialspoint, 2011), and is also available under a variety of proprietary licenses. Total interfaces were implemented using HTML, CSS, JavaScript, jQuery and Bootstrap.

Testing and Evaluation

During this phase, the bottlenecks or performance deviations were identified in the Event Management System and whether the performance of the software was influenced by the software bugs was investigated. Performance evaluation is important to identify the speed, capacity and stability of the system. At each level, our modules were tested through unit testing, integration testing and system integration testing. Each stage, there were some deviations. Then the deviations were corrected. After that, the sections were retested by entering records in the system. As a result, the system would be a very useful system to record daily activities and manage those effectively.

Conclusion

Achievements

A web-based system for Event Script Ltd. was implemented within the stipulated time. Event Script was able to overcome the limitations and issues of the existing system through the new system.

Limitations

The complete online booking system could not be facilitated due to some practical issues. The online payment system could not be included.

Future enhancements

More modules such as expenses, salary should be facilitated. Further, it is hoped to develop a mobile application to be connected to the system.

References

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